

Supplementary Material 1

Detailed description of the Stroll exercises

	<i>Description of the exercise</i>	<i>Exercise settings</i>	<i>Feedback</i>
<p>Smash</p>	<p>An AR rehabilitation exercise designed to train gait, dynamic balance, weight shifting, turning and cross body rotations through interactive boxing movements.</p> <p>The goal is to smash items that appear on multiple pillars. The placement of items across multiple pillars encourages walking, turning, and controlled movement transitions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise (1-10 minutes) • Hand mode (any, alternating, left-right ratio) • Number of pillars (2-10, auto) • Punch repetitions (2, 3-10, 11-20, 21-30 punches to smash an item) <p><i>Advanced settings</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Left-right ratio (to select punches to be performed by desired upper limb) • Inhibition (avoid punching the TNT mole) • Reaction speed (pop the balloon) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of prescribed and performed punches • Meters walked • Score (based on number of items smashed, TNT moles avoided, balloons popped and meters walked) <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Adherence • Challenge score • Meters walked • Number of punches • Score
<p>Mole Patrolll</p>	<p>An AR goal-directed rehabilitation exercise designed to improve gait initiation, walking adaptability, balance, turning, stopping, and lower-body strength (when played in squat mode).</p> <p>The goal is to stomp as many moles as possible before they disappear. Players must scan their surroundings, spot the moles as they pop up, and react quickly, either stomping with both feet or squatting, depending on the chosen User mode.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise (1-10 minutes) • Reaction time (3-30 seconds, unlimited) • User mode (stomp, squat) • Number of mole positions (5–25, auto) <p><i>Advanced settings</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Object avoidance (1-3 tortoises) • Decision making (step on the golden mole) Inhibition (avoid stepping on the TNT mole) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meters walked • Score (based on number of moles stomped, TNT moles and turtles avoided, and meters walked) <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Adherence • Challenge score • Meters walked • Number of moles spawned • Number of squats (in squat used mode) • Score
<p>Hot Buttons</p>	<p>An AR dynamic reaching exercise designed to train functional reaching, reaction time, coordination, visual scanning and dynamic balance.</p> <p>The goal is to press the button that lights up before it disappears. Buttons are presented in a customizable grid formation, appearing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise (1-10 minutes) • Reaction time (1-15 seconds, unlimited) • Hand mode (any, left-right ratio) • Grid orientation (vertical, horizontal, supine) • Columns (1-5) • Rows (1–5) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of buttons pressed in a streak (i.e., pressing two or more buttons in a row with the prescribed hand) • Score (based on number of buttons pressed) <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score

	across multiple rows and columns in a variety of (curved) layouts from horizontal, vertical and inverted.	<p><i>Advanced settings</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Left-right ratio (to select preference for desired upper limb rehabilitation) • Neglect ratio (to specifically target spatial or attentional deficits) • Reach distance (40-90 cm, only active with vertical grid) • Grid curve (0, 45, 90 degrees) 	<p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Adherence • Challenge score • Number of reach repetitions • Number of correct buttons pressed • Reaction time • Score
<p><i>Basketballl</i></p>	<p>An AR rehabilitation exercise designed to train both lower-limb and upper limb strength, dynamic balance, coordination, endurance and core strength through engaging sit-to-stand, squat-to-stand, or stationary activities.</p> <p>The goal is to score as many points as possible by completing movements to unlock basketballs and shooting them into the hoop.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise: (1-10 minutes) • User mode (sit-to-stand, squat, stationary) • Hand mode (any, left, right, bilateral, randomized) • Sit-to-stands or squats repetitions (1-15) • Shot difficulty (easy, medium, hard) <p><i>Advanced settings</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of racks (1, 3) • Moving hoop • Matching (numbers, letters, shapes) • Sequence (only available with matching turned on) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of prescribed and performed sit-to-stands or squats • Number of baskets scored • Score (based on number of sit-to-stands or squats and baskets scored, if matching or sequence is turned on) <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Adherence • Challenge score • Number of sit-to-stands or squats • Shots thrown • Baskets scored • Score
<p><i>Puzzle Walk</i></p>	<p>An AR goal-directed rehabilitation exercise designed to train gait, dynamic balance, turning, stopping, functional reaching, and upper-limb coordination.</p> <p>The goal is to find scattered puzzle pieces around the training space, reach to pick them up, and place them onto the easel to complete as many puzzles as possible before the allocated time runs out. Puzzle pieces can be placed at different heights, challenging players to reach at high, head, shoulder, hip, knee, or floor levels for a full range of motion.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise (1-10 minutes) • Hand mode (any, left-right ratio) • Puzzle piece heights (high, head, shoulder, hip, knee, floor) <p><i>Advanced settings</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Left-right ratio (to select preference for desired upper limb rehabilitation) • Hand rotation task • Matching (numbers, letters, shapes) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of prescribed and collected puzzle pieces • Score (based on meters walked, puzzle pieces collected and correctly placed, if hand rotation or matching is turned on) <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Adherence • Challenge score • Meters walked • Number of puzzle pieces collected and placed • Score